

► Flood Management System with Sound Early Warnings for Kalu Ganga at Ratnapura

Concept Paper

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After analyzing more than 100 years daily precipitation data in Ratnapura meteorological station and investigating monthly mean rainfall as well as annual rainfall it was found that annual rainfall is fluctuating between 3000mm to 4000mm. Not only that, it was observed that peak average monthly rainfall occurs in May, June months and September, November months. Further, almost all the medium and major flood event occur after dry water year and the same situation was noticed in the year 2016. Therefore I predicted the total rainfall in the year 2017 has given a warning.

For conclusion, flood management system and early warning system may be a remedy for above unbalance environmental situation.

Abstract: Sri Lanka is highly Sensitive Island for natural disasters. It is located in the Indian Ocean therefore sudden climatic changes occur. Research on climatic changes and its patterns around Sri Lanka will be useful to realize the natural disasters like flood and landslide which are more common and frequent. Minor floods occur every year in between May to December. A major flood has occurred in Kalu Ganga basin in the year, 2003 and 2017 recently. The major flood has damaged lives, assets, cultivations, and infrastructure causing subsequent impact on sanitary problems, diseases, resettlement issues. Western, Southern and Sabaragamuwa provinces are constantly affected by the flood. Ratnapura district frequently faces the challenges of flood hazards from May to September every year. The South-West monsoon arrives with carrying 2000mm of rainwater (50% of total annual rainfall) and the inter-monsoon period from October to November carrying 1000mm of rainwater (22% of total annual rainfall). Although annual rainfall of 4000mm affects to Ratnapura, above two periods are the heavy rainy seasons that caused for flooding. It aggravates when there is a low pressure created in Bengal bay of Indian Ocean. Kalu River is originating from Adam's Peak at an elevation over 2250m above mean sea level (MSL). It flows through Ratnapura town, which located in a comparatively lowland at about 18m to 305m (MSL) and several tributaries are joined in between. It flows through Ratnapura towards the sea at Kaluthara. Ratnapura low lying riverine area is inundated in peak rainy season. According to historical data, more than 300mm rainfall within 24 hours at upper catchment sometimes caused a major flood at the urbanized area. There are not any flood controlling or warning systems in the current situation. There are new techniques practicing in Japan to mitigate and control the flood. For example, Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) disseminates warning and information about disaster via various channels in order to reach people surely and quickly, for example, JMA has given an emergency warning during the Typhoon Man-Yi in 2013. Sri Lanka can adapt those technics to mitigate the disaster risk reduction program.

Key Words: Flood, Rainfall, Disasters, Catchment, Warning

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Riverine flooding are intensified by the climate changes and anthropogenic activities. For example, urbanization is a common practice in the world and more significant to the mountainous regions. It is widely agreed over the world that the global warming is a reality and causes climatic changes including changes in rainfall patterns. In recent decades, the intensity of rainfalls over a shorter period of time has been increased together with the frequency of such intense events. Meanwhile, human activities in upstream catchments such as de-forestation, changing natural land-use by agriculture activities have caused to decrease infiltration and increase surface runoff through the catchments. Also due to the soil erosion caused by losing vegetation cover of the catchment and higher velocities of runoff cause more sedimentation in the rivers. All of these factors

ultimately cause flooding in the low land riverine cities. Modern landscaping technical gives less time of concentration for runoff water. There are number of studies conducted on flooding and their possible prevention and mitigation. However, the methods that have been used in one case might not be suitable for the other.

This concept paper is based on analyzing past rainfall events and introducing an early warning system for Kalu Ganga. It also predict flooding in the mountainous riverine city of Ratnapura. The first part of this research will focus on the methods to increase the time of warning and second part will discuss the increase of the infiltration by introducing some storage tanks at the upstream catchment of Kalu Ganga. These methods can be, diverting excess runoff by providing eco-friendly structures, increasing surface roughness by re-introducing vegetation covers and providing additional temporary storage tanks at suitable locations in the upper catchment. Structural mitigation methods will discuss in another paper.

1.1 Background

Kalu Ganga is the third longest river (110 km) in Sri Lanka originating from Adam’s peak at an elevation over 2000m above Mean Sea Level (MSL) discharging 4000MCM annually to the sea. It flows through Ratnapura town, which situated in a comparatively low land at about 18 m (MSL), where flooding is a common phenomenon whenever there is heavy rainfall over the peak range (upstream catchment). Several tributaries covering a catchment area of 603 km² contribute to Kalu Ganga in its’ section through Malwala to Ratnapura while Wey Ganga River through Kahawatta area joins Kalu Ganga at Ratnapura town adding a higher flood risk to the main town. The inadequacy of river gradient of 0.15 m/km downstream from Ratnapura town to Kaluthara to convey the excess water surging to the town from both rivers during heavy rains increases the risk of town being flooded frequently. Regular monsoon rains cause minor floods and landslide in low lying areas of Ratnapura, while occasional torrential rains caused by cyclonic storms originating in the Bay of Bengal in a frequency of once in about a decade cause major floods in both the Ratnapura and Kalutara districts. There are High Flood Level’s (HFL) marked on

historical buildings around the city area in Ratnapura. Maximum recorded flood was in 1947 flood, but more damages were occurred in 2003, 18th May flood.

2.0 RATIONALE

Flood threats in Ratnapura town have caused many deaths and millions of rupees damages to properties and infrastructure. Such major floods were occurred in the recent past in 1992, 2003 and 2017. In the year 2003, 18th May flood caused 122 deaths and had affected 34,000 families. Destruction created by it also costs over one thousand million rupees including houses, schools, public buildings, roadways, irrigation schemes, and industries. Even though the climate and geometry of river cannot be changed or controlled, the human activities in the upper catchment can be controlled and changes to catchment surface and early warning system may be a remedy for above unbalance environmental situation.

Damage Report of 2017 May 26th Flood (Flood and Landslide) - Ratnapura District		
Affected Numbers of Divisional Sectarian	17	
Affected Numbers of Grama Niladari Division	423	
Affected Numbers of Families	60,080	
Affected Numbers of Members	235,197	
Numbers of Refugee Centers	221	
Refugee of Families	11,865	
Refugee of Members	47,064	
Numbers of Deaths	86	
Numbers of Missing	15	
House Damages		
	Full	721
	Half	10,944
Damage of House - hold Goods and Equipment		12,556
Nunbers of Resettlement Families		
	Families at Land slide Areas	229
	Families at Land slide Prone Areas	1,290
	Families at Flood Prone Areas	212
Cost need for Reconstruction of Infrastructures		Rs. 15,254,000.62

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Aim/ Objective

In this concept paper, I am going to describe how I analyzed rainfall pattern in Ratnapura riverine region, which is a major source of water to a Kalu Ganga and a substantial part of Ratnapura, transported through the river to Kaluthara district that originates from the central mountains.

Rainfall patterns of an area are influenced by topography, and topography is always an expression of the local geology. Therefore an intimate relationship between rainfall intensity, local geology, and study of local rainfall records, therefore, must be an early part of all hydrological investigations. Where no local recording stations exist, expert advice should be taken as to how the nearest available records can best be extrapolated for the station being studied. Close attention must be paid to

the relation between the rainfalls during the period of site study and the long-term average, since if any major deviation from the normal is occurring, then the suitable allowance for the effect of this must be made. Rainfall patterns of an area are influenced by topography, and topography is always an expression of the local geology. Therefore an intimate relationship between rainfall intensity, local geology, and study of local rainfall records, therefore, must be an early part of all hydrological investigations. Where no local recording stations exist, expert advice should be taken as to how the nearest available records can best be extrapolated for the station being studied. Close attention must be paid to the relation between the rainfalls during the period of site study and the long-term average, since if any major deviation from the normal is occurring, then the suitable allowance for the effect of this must be made.

Before analysis of long-term rainfall trends in Ratnapura riverine region, the identity of the trends in annual rainfall, inter-annual as well as intra-annual rainfall trends are most important. Finally investigating of changing of rainfall pattern will analyse to understand the adverse impacts of the flood. Firstly daily data were collected from about 100 years period from the Ratnapura gauging station which has been maintained by Meteorology Department. The river gauges data was maintained by Irrigation Department.

3.2 Experimental Setup/Data Collection

The missing data of the rest were filled from neighboring stations using a correlation and inverse distance algorithm. Then the seasonal and annual rainfall at each year is computed. Next, the trend is estimated by filing a linear regression line for each station for annual rainfall. By inspecting the results, the long-

Month	Avarage RF/(mm)	Cumulative RF/(mm)
Jan	134.3	134.3
Feb	135.6	269.9
Mar	222.2	492.1
Apr	334.5	826.6
May	468.1	1294.7
Jun	459.5	1754.2
Jul	311.3	2065.5
Aug	301.7	2367.2
Sep	365.4	2732.6
Oct	467.4	3200.0
Nov	360.6	3560.6
Dec	218.2	3778.8
TOTAL	3778.8	

term rainfall trends, as well as the rainfall anomalies, were observed. Feed data into the spreadsheet (Ex. MS Excel), and using formulas and function, a database was created. Computer software will help to analyze the data and it will find a correlation between each and every two databases. Using that correlation table we found missing data. For that we use the following formula;

$$\frac{Y_2 - X_2}{Y_1 - X_1} = (g) \frac{S_2}{S_1}$$

- g = Correlation coefficient between station 1 and 2
- Y₁ = Rainfall value of station 1
- X₁ = Mean value of the rainfall data in station 1
- S₁ = Standard deviation of the rainfall data in station 1
- Y₂ = Rainfall value of station 2
- X₂ = Mean value of the rainfall data in station 2
- S₂ = Standard deviation of the rainfall data in station 2

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

Annual rainfall was computed and generated the graph against time (year). It illustrated the variation of annual rainfall falls between 3000mm to 4000mm. According to research done by Mr. Chandrapala L, annual variability of rainfall in terms of long-term average in the year, 1880 to 2000 is ± 400mm. This concludes that annual rainfall is not changing significantly because of climate change but

maximum and minimum temperature rises and that affects the rainfall pattern. For example, intensity and quantity of precipitation changing overpass recent years. Thereafter monthly average rainfall was

$$Y = -0.2849X + 12352; \text{ Year 2016 RF Pattern}$$

$$Y = 0.4766X - 19960; \text{ Average RF Pattern}$$

calculated and graphed. The average annual rainfall is around 3778.8mm and there are two peaks of annual rainfall distribution. One peak is May-June months and the second peak is October-November months. The first peak, people of Sabaragamuwa traditionally named as “45 days flood” (rain comes after 45 days from Sinhala-Hindu New Year) and for the second peak, they named as “Perahera flood (rain comes after finished the parade of Saman Dewale)

With the knowledge of total annual rainfall variation as well as the average monthly distribution of rainfall of Ratnapura station, data set of 2016 rainfall were graphed. It was shown that total received rainfall of 2016 well below to average valve. Total annual rainfall for the year 2016 is about 2783.4mm and it is nearly 1000mm less than normal. The pattern of the monthly mean rainfall on the year 2016 differs from its average. Linear trend line equation fixed to all year average rainfall pattern gives gradient, $m=0.4766$ and linear trend line equation fixed to the year 2016 rainfall pattern gives gradient, $m= -0.2849$. The difference of above mention lines is 370 degrees which are considered high value.

3.4 Outcomes

Critical floods in Ratnapura, which occurred in 1913, 1940, 1941, 1947 and 2003 reached levels closer to 24.0m (MSL). In addition to

those critical floods, major floods were occurred in 1857, 1872, 1893, 1924, 1947, 1957, 1969, 1975, 1978, 1982, 1988, 1989 and 1993. These floods reached levels above 21.0m. (MSL). Flood in Ratnapura during the period from 15th to 18th of May 2003, it was reported that this flood ranked the fifth worst flood according to records. However, the damage was mainly due to the settlement of people in areas prone to landslides and floods. It is now reported that the total damage to the property is about Rs. 1,050 Mn. due to floods and landslides and 133 people died in Kalu the Ganga basin during that flood. Another critical flood came in the year 2017 May 26th, the dry year of 2016 help to predict last flood event it should be further analysis to find the suitable relationship between dry and wet years. I was able to of predict 2017 May flood before three months and convey the message from varies channels such as district-level forums, meetings, and media. Because of that,

people fully aware of situation hence dead count was reduced. But modern lifestyle is different hence general public cannot always be alert. Therefore a mechanism needs for convey the immediate warning message during heavy rain in the upstream catchment.

3.5 Timeline

Firstly, need to collect all the rainfall and river level data of particular station and correction should apply before making graphs.

Secondly, comparative graphs should be made with selected year rainfall and monthly normal rainfall and fix the trend line to find out the gradient difference between the graphs.

Thirdly, Comparison of gradient difference of the graphs with river gauge reading needs to be done to find out dry and wet relationship.

4.0 SUPPORT

Government support is needed for further development of this metrology. One can choose this concept paper as an undergraduate or any highest studies research proposal.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Global warming could probably be responsible for these devastating extreme weather events resulting in natural disasters in Sri Lanka. These events might become more frequent, persistent and intense in the future. Flooding of Ratnapura town due to Kalu Ganga is a frequent occurrence. Records of floods are available from 1850. The Ratnapura town gets submerged when river

level rises above 18.5m (MSL) and the worst floods, which occurred in 1913, 1940, 1941, 1947 and 2003 reached levels closer to 24.0m (MSL). In addition to those critical floods, major floods occurred in 1857, 1872, 1893, 1924, 1947, 1957, 1969, 1975, 1978, 1982, 1988, 1989 and 1993. These floods have reached levels above 21.0m (MSL). A severe storm in the year 2003, May 18th caused heavy flooding in the Kalu Ganga. The intensity of this storm as measured in Ratnapura was 40mm of rainfall in 15 minutes and 280mm in 6 hours. This unusually intense rainfall caused economy lost was high, even though the number of casualties was relatively low. According to historical data, more than 300mm rainfall in 24 hours of upper catchment sometimes caused a major flood into the urbanized area. There are not any flood controlling or warning systems in the current situation. New techniques practice in other countries must be adopted to mitigate and control the flood.

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